

Recommended citation: Sillasen, M. K., Thomassen, M. L., Krogh, L. B., & Auner, S. (2018). Engineering translated to primary schools. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1248-1257). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672847.

Engineering translated to primary schools

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Conference Key Areas: Innovative teaching and learning methods, Curriculum development, Educational and Organizational development

Keywords: Engineering, Primary schools, Denmark

1: INTRODUCTION

Denmark will lack 13.500 engineers & science-candidates (Engineer the Future, 2015) and 30.000 technicians in 2025 (Danish Industry Association, 2015), if the nation does not consider extraordinary educational efforts to fill in these gaps. To meet these challenges the Danish government has launched a STEM-strategy for the entire

educational system, where engineering is recommended as a teaching strategy in schools to strengthen pupils' scientific and technological literacy (Danish Government, 2018). STEM is an abbreviation for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. However, the recruitment challenge is not the only valid argument for focusing on engineering in schools. Another argument is to prevent, that pupils enter society as technological illiterates. Teaching concerning both the E and T in STEM can lead to technological literacy and interest in science and technology. It is part of modern literacy to have an understanding about, where the technology that surrounds us and defines our lives originates. al

For this reason we propose the following research question:

How can technological literacy be strengthened through initiatives in primary schools in Denmark?

To find the answer a case study has been conducted on the project "Engineering in School" (EiS). EiS is a large scale (4 municipalities, 65 schools, 520 teachers), longitudinal (2017-2020) project that integrates the development of curriculum materials, didactical models for teaching, collaborative teacher professional development (TPD) and science events, for primary schools in Denmark (The Danish education system is presented in appendix 1).

The development of curriculum materials and didactical models are predominantly inspired by design criterias from the American engineering programme Engineering is Elementary (Engineering is Elementary, 2018). The TPD-programme is inspired by the Danish QUEST-project and designed with reference to Guskeys criterias for effective TPD (Nielsen & Sillasen, 2014). According to Guskey (2003) effective TPD is based on 1) developing teacher pedagogical content knowledge, 2) ample time and resources for actionlearning, 3) introduction to assessment strategies, 4) collegial collaborations and knowledgesharing in schoolbased contexts.

2: METHODS

Since engineering is a new concept in the Danish school context there was from the outset a need to learn about engineering as a teaching strategy and the most optimum way to structure engineering curriculum materials. To meet these challenges the EiS-project is divided into five phases (see figure 1): Desk research, developing, testing, engagement and dissemination. The desk research (phase 1) started with a literature review with the aim to identify principles of good engineering teaching practices, existing resources for building teacher professional development (TPD) and as a byproduct the research was published in a Danish math and science didactical journal (Sillasen, Daugbjerg, Nielsen, 2017). In phase 2-3 we used this knowledge base to further develop and test didactical theory, curriculum materials and a TPD-programme. During these phases empirical data was collected from multiple sources giving feedback to didactical and curriculum developers. Through action learning we collected teachers selfreports about their experiments with engineering activities in their own teaching practices and conducted observational studies of the teachers in action. Pre- and postsurveys distributed in phase 3 mapped pupil and teachers learning outcome and attitudes towards engineering activities. Furthermore, a focus group was formed with representatives from university engineering departments. The purpose of the focus group was to give feedback on and further develop the engineering didactical models. Results from these investigations will be presented and

discussed below. In phase 4 (2018) we upscale the TPD intervention in the four municipalities to include 65 schools and 520 teachers. Phase 5 (2019) is dissemination in two directions: To other schools in the four initial municipalities and to other municipalities. When the project ends in 2020 the aim is that 900 teachers have participated in engineering TPD and that we have tested 12 engineering curriculum activities available for teachers through open access.

Figure 1: EiS phases of development

The EiS-project is designed based on characteristics of Design Based Research (The Design-based Research Collective, 2003). It depicts the complexity of a DBR-project in the sense that we simultaneously experiment with learning environments, develop theories of learning engineering, enactment, design and redesign of prototypes of didactical models and curriculum materials.

3: RESULTS

In this section we present examples of the didactical models, curriculum materials, TPD-model and assessment results which is the outcome of phase 3 and phase 4.

3.1: The Engineering Design Process model

The purpose of doing engineering in schools is to raise pupils' interest and strengthen their technological literacy and STEM competences. Through the engineering didactical model, EiS clarify for pupils what challenges engineers work with and methods they use for problem solving. The teaching must reflect the engineering process - problem analysis, generating ideas, using existing knowledge and iterative improvement of prototypes - that engineers use when they solve problems or develop novel technological innovations. However, it is important to recognize that working with engineering problems in a school context is different from the situation when engineers solve real-world-problems. Pupils are not engineers working in a big company. In a school setting it is only partially possible to situate pupils in the same situation as engineers when they are solving a real-world-problem. When developing effective didactic models for engineering in schools we have to careful select characteristic engineering features that is relevant to produce meaningful teaching. For this reason it is not the aim for schools to educate new engineers or create innovative products that can be sold. No. The aim of doing engineering in schools is for pupils to gain experiences with engineering as a strategy to solve problems and strengthen their self-awareness about own capabilities to solve problems, while learning and utilizing science and technology at their level. From teachers experiments with engineering in phase 2 and 3 we learned, that two of the most important engineering features that pupils learn is: 1) Working with the Engineering Design Process (See figure 2) and 2) knowledge about material properties necessary for solving a given challenge. These findings are supported by the Engineering is Elementary programme (Cunningham, 2017).

In Project EiS we developed an Engineering Design Proces-model (figure 2) which consisted of seven workprocesses: Understand challenge, explore, develop ideas, plan, create, improve and present solution.

Figure 2: Engineering Design Proces-model

Engineering-activities in a school context is organized as projects, where pupils work with a technological challenge that starts with *understanding the challenge* and ends with *presenting the solution* (See figure 2). Naturally, evaluation of the product and

process is done either continuously or at the end of the process, to solidify the learning outcome. The teacher can infuse authenticity into the engineering activity by framing the challenge through a narrative, that can contextualize the problem, motivate and legitimize the pupils to work with it. When pupils are presenting their solution, the teacher must have focus on two questions: What scientific knowledge have the pupils learned and how was the learning process? When answering these questions pupils automatically reconsider the initial challenge retrospectively and assess to what degree they have solved the challenge.

In between the beginning and the end pupils work with five work processes. We have not indicated that these work processes follow a particular succession. From teacher feedback we learned, that pupil's problem solving strategy takes different paths. However there was a distinction between whether the engineering activities was done in lower grades (grade 1-4) or upper grades (grade 5-7). In grade 1-4 the pupils primarily iterated between *creating* and *improving* their prototypes. While in the upper grades pupils have developed more reflective skills to put emphasis on *developing*, *planning* and *exploring* their prototyping in a systematic manner.

The other important feature is that pupils learn *about* material properties to construct a prototype. A central part of creating or improving the prototype to meet the constraints of the initial challenge is for pupils to consider which materials can be used to solve the challenge most optimal. For this reason the exploration process becomes important, because this is where pupils gather knowledge about what types of materials might be most suitable to build the prototype.

While the EDP model support the scaffolding, it is important that teachers initially identifies learning goals and consider the degree of freedom the pupils are allowed during the different phases of the process. To further support teachers educational design curriculum materials is developed and the basic principles for the materials is presented in the following section.

3.2: Curriculum materials

A unique feature in the EiS-project is that curriculum materials are developed in close conjunction with the didactical models. This provided space for a rich discussion between the didactical developers and the curriculum developers to ensure quality in both components. From the outset a cohorte of teachers was interviewed to determine design characteristics for good engineering teaching materials. These design characteristic were used to produce the first version of teaching materials that subsequently was tested in phase 3 and 4. As part of this testing the design criterias was also assessed and discussed with the participating teachers. Based on this evaluation a refined set of design criterias emerged (Se table 1).

Table 1: Design criterias for curriculum materials. Quality engineering teaching material integrates a majority of these criterias.

Design criteria	Comment
EDP-model	Pupils work proces is guided by the EDP-model (figure 2)
STEM curriculum	The engineering activities relates to STEM subjects
Narrative context	A narrative situates the engineering challenge in a real-world-context.
Multiple solutions	The challenge, materials and constraints opens for multiple ways to solve the problem.
Materials	Pupils should be able to gain experiences with different materials and tools to manipulate materials.
Degrees-of-freedom	An engineering activity should enable pupils to solve the challenge with various degrees-of-freedom.
Practical-constructive-optimizing process	Pupils construct a prototype that can be improved through iterative testing and re-design.
Ethics	The challenge should include an ethical aspect. E.g. the solution might solve a challenge that is a real-world-problem that improve life quality for humanity.

The purpose of the curriculum materials is to support pupils' autonomous work with engineering activities. For this reason the curriculum materials is organized differently than traditional science textbooks and experiments. Since engineering is basically a systematically problembased work proces, the materials is designed to support pupil work in the different work processes in the EDP-model (figure 2). Thus a curriculum materials consists of a narrative, worksheets for each EDP-workproces and additional resources for exploring material properties and scientific knowledge that can support pupil learning. Curriculum materials are available at www.astra.dk/engineering .

3.3: Teacher training model

The EiS TPD-programme is designed using principles of professional learning communities (Stoll et al, 2006) and combines three activities: Fading support, scaffolding and increasing teacher responsibility during workshop activities and experimenting with engineering in their own practice (Van der Pol et al, 2010). During phase 3 and 4 of the EiS-project the TPD-program was tested and upscaled to full capacity. The TPD-programme was organized as two iterative action learning cycles where teachers in the initial two day workshop was introduced to engineering didactical models and curriculum materials (Se figure 3) followed by a period of experimenting with engineering activities in their own teaching practice. In the second iteration teachers were encouraged to invite other teachers to engage in experimenting with engineering activities through a collaborative collegial process thereby enhancing dissemination of engineering activities within the local learning community within a school.

Figure 3: TPD-model

3.4: Evaluation

The EiS project has been continuously evaluated on multiple levels. The engineering didactical models has been revised based on feedback from the focus group and the teachers who has worked with it in practice. The teachers also evaluated the TDP-program, through surveys and oral feedback. Pupils and teacher learning outcome was assessed using pre- and postsurveys in phase 3. Teachers were asked about their attitudes towards engineering as a teaching practice in schools and their pupils learning outcome. The results showed significant increase in teachers attitude regarding engineering as increasing pupils motivation, creativity and innovation. They also learn better to investigate problems more systematically. These results resonates with pupils results. Pupils reported that engineering is a good variation to “normal” science activities, engineering helped them to better understand science concepts and that teachers are better to scaffold pupils work. Pupils would like to have more engineering activities in the curriculum. Our presentation on the SEFI-conference will elaborate these results.

4: CONCLUSION

Based on our preliminary research it appears effective to develop a tailored engineering didactics for primary schools in conjunction with curriculum materials and spread through a TPD program. In this case, it is yet too early to conclude anything in relation to the long term effects on technological literacy and choice of career paths. Research conducted in relation to the Engineering is Elementary program, suggests that working with engineering in primary school have a positive effect on building science and math skills, it promote classroom equity by accommodating different learning styles (Cassidy, 2004) and pupils become more aware of diverse opportunities for careers including engineering, science and technical careers (Engineering is Elementary, 2018).

5: DISCUSSION

The first four phases of the EiS-project revealed some challenges that we will address in this section.

5.1: Challenges

The biggest success in EiS is that engineering has improved the teaching in primary science for the teachers participating in the project. Curriculum activities in Danish primary science have not developed significantly during the last 15-20 years. From the teachers' self-reports we learned that engineering has improved the pupil learning and also introduces new ideas into the teaching practice. Despite that teachers report, that time, materials and planning engineering activities takes its toll the reward is better science teaching and learning opportunities for the pupils.

Another challenge is to develop quality curriculum materials that enables pupils to learn science and technology. Experiences for the EiS project and the American EiE-programme have shown, that developing and testing engineering teaching materials is a lengthy and cumbersome process. It seems that collaboration between engineering faculties and teacher training institutes can be productive regarding innovating new materials, and research connected to EiE shows it has a positive effect on the pupils' science knowledge and technical skills. It is not possible yet to measure if the EiS project has the positive effect of enabling and inspiring pupils to further education with in science, technology and engineering, but preliminary research shows it has a positive effect on attitude and innovative skills. The challenge is that engineering is competing with other novel initiatives on the educational arena. The large foundations in Danish commerce have realized, that to ensure future generations of a skilled laborforce they must invest in the educational system. Several foundations have launched large funding programmes for educational innovation. The challenge for schools is to balance their interest in getting involved in innovative projects with the teaching activities in schools. Pupils still need to be taught basic science and math even if their teachers are involved in developmental activities.

5.2: Future aspirations

The EiS-project revealed many possibilities. The next step in the EiS-project is to spread and solidify EiS in the participating municipalities. Focus will also be on disseminating engineering in schools in new municipalities in Denmark. During 2018 the EiS-project have experienced increased publicity and other municipalities and schools have shown an increased interest. Further development of curriculum materials is also an opportunity, materials focusing on utilizing specific technologies could strengthen the current collection. To ensure progression in STEM education in Denmark an extension of EiS could be to develop the engineering didactics and curriculum materials for upper secondary education.

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Appendix 1: The Danish Education System

* International Standard Classification of Education

Source: Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark

http://www.netpublikationer.dk/um/8870/images/image_4-n8gG_2.jpg